

MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION QUALITY: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the fundamental approaches to assessing the quality of education in accordance with the requirements of the federal educational program for primary general education. The trend in the effectiveness of independent monitoring of the quality of education in the form of all-Russian testing works has been analyzed in recent years. A number of significant reasons determining the potential educational failure of primary school graduates have been identified and practical recommendations have been proposed to help mitigate the most common difficulties of students.*

Keywords: *primary school students, assessment of the quality of students training, all-Russian testing, federal educational program of primary general education, improving the work of a primary school teacher, pedagogical techniques for eliminating difficulties.*

INTRODUCTION. At the present stage of global systemic changes in society, the issue of transforming the unstable and complex VUCA world with its uncertainty and ambiguity into the format of a deeply disturbing, non-linear, and therefore quite difficult to understand BANI world with a very illusory stability, ready to collapse at any moment is being increasingly discussed.

The new acronym to describe the modern world, proposed by futurologist D. Cascio, does not generate new meanings, but allows humanity to comprehend what is happening around. In these conditions, the well-known model of lifelong continuous education is increasingly gaining its position, allowing you to permanently update knowledge, update your skills and abilities, or acquire fundamentally new competencies - learn, retrain and master new professions, integrating into a multipolar world.

Against this background, the role of general education is rapidly increasing, and before our eyes, the domestic school ceases to perform only the function of mass education of the younger generation, becoming the focus of familiarization with traditional Russian values, the internalization of the national cultural code, the acquisition of social experience, the formation of functional literacy, which, undoubtedly, is becoming a stable trigger for self-education, a driver of self-development and a stable vector for moving forward. This, in turn, determines the search for relevant tools and objective approaches to assessing the achievement of planned educational results of students [8; 9;12; 16-18].

Based on the current legislation of the Russian Federation, general education organizations develop and implement the basic educational program of primary general education (hereinafter referred to as the FEP IEO) in accordance with the requirements of the Federal Basic General Education Program of Primary General Education (hereinafter referred to as the FOP IEO), approved by order of the Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation No. 372 of May 18 2023, which determines the unified planned results of mastering the educational program, the

volume and content of education at the level of primary general education. In organizing the procedure for assessing the educational results of junior schoolchildren, in addition to the system-activity and level ones, an integrated approach is implemented, which involves monitoring dynamic indicators of achievement of subject, meta-subject and personal results using a variety of methods and forms of assessment that complement each other.

When assessing personal results in accordance with paragraph 19.16 of the FOP NEO, the formation of the foundations of Russian civic identity, value systems and socially significant qualities of students, their readiness for self-development, sustainable manifestation of educational and cognitive motivation and active participation in socially significant activities are analyzed. Taking into account the characteristics of personal results, based on the requirements of paragraph 19.17 of the FOP NEO, it is envisaged to assess whether an elementary school graduate has such qualities as educational and cognitive motivation, the ability to plan his own educational activities, exercise self-control and self-assessment.

Diagnostics of the level of achievement of meta-subject results includes an analysis of the ability of junior schoolchildren to perform educational tasks and resolve extra-curricular situations that require confident mastery of all groups of universal learning activities (hereinafter referred to as UAL), and is carried out through monitoring the entire set of cognitive, communicative and regulatory UAL.

The objective of assessing subject results in accordance with the content of the FOP of the NEO is the ability of students to solve educational, cognitive and educational and practical tasks built on the main content of academic subjects, taking into account the meta-subject actions being formed. In accordance with paragraph 19.34 of the FOP of the NEO, the level of mastery of subject results is determined within the framework of in-school assessment procedures for current, thematic, intermediate and final control. It is important to note that, based on clause 19.35 of the FOP of the IEO, the annex to the OOP of the IEO must record the specifics of assessing subject results.

The problem of transforming generally accepted and actively used tools for assessing the quality of general education does not leave the minds of participants in educational relations, recently provoking a fairly active professional and public discourse on the issue of the reasonableness of conducting all-Russian testing works (hereinafter referred to as the All-Russian Test Work) as a form of independent monitoring of students' educational performance [4, 7-15].

The issue of objectivity and maximum transparency of the procedure for monitoring and assessing the quality of general education is the focus of special attention of the Federal Service for Supervision in Education and Science (Rosobrnadzor), which plans to move away from the usual format for conducting educational programs and organize assessment procedures exclusively using computer technologies. The changes will affect both the time it takes to complete the task and the marks received by students for it, which will become not just final, but will become more important [1]. For our part, we note that all VPR materials for primary schools, which are developed on the basis of the Federal Institute for Education Quality Assessment (FIAKO), are of a diagnostic nature, allowing not only to objectively assess the success of mastering the planned results of the educational educational program, but also to judge the effectiveness of the forms and methods used, means, approaches, methods of work of a primary school teacher.

Analytical data from the implementation of educational tasks over the past few years allow teachers to identify a number of significant reasons that determine the potential educational failure

of primary school graduates: lack of confident skills in semantic reading of texts of various genres and the algorithm for working with them; the ability to convincingly express one's own point of view and construct a speech statement in oral and written forms, using the means of language; insufficient level of logical and algorithmic thinking; the presence of significant gaps in basic subject knowledge in individual sections of the curriculum and serious deficiencies in the system of meta-subject activities.

To eliminate these reasons that impede not only the successful mastery of educational programs in the subjects of the curriculum, but also the meaningful use of acquired knowledge mastered by UUD in solving educational and life problems, primary school teachers can be recommended to include a system of tasks in the content of educational and extracurricular activities of younger schoolchildren, which can contribute to the formation of:

- confident skill in semantic reading of texts containing various formats for presenting information (text, map, diagram, drawing, plan, table, drawing, etc.);
- the ability to cogently express one's point of view, with sufficient completeness and accuracy to construct a speech statement in oral and written form in accordance with the educational task;
- logical operations, algorithmic and spatial thinking [3; 5; 10].

As part of the E-rate overhaul, the FCC also approved a series of regulatory changes aimed at leveling the playing field for rural and remote schools, which often face two big struggles: accessing the fiber-optic cables that experts say are essential to meeting the FCC's long-term goals, and finding affordable rates. Infrastructure in some contexts can also be taken to include learning devices, digital content, and the policies and guidelines that govern how they are expected to be used in schools (such as "responsible use policies" and "digital citizenship" programs aimed to ensure that students and staff are using technology appropriately and in support of learning goals.) Another big—and often overlooked—aspect of infrastructure is what's known as interoperability. Essentially, the term refers to common standards and protocols for formatting and handling data so that information can be shared between software programs. A number of frameworks outline data interoperability standards for different purposes. Many hope to see the field settle on common standards in the coming years. One big trend for schools involves trying to make sure that what happens online is connected with what happens during face-to-face interactions with teachers. That could involve giving teachers a say in selecting the software that students use, for example, or making a concerted effort to ensure online programs provide teachers with data that is useful in making timely instructional decisions. Another trend involves boosting students' access to the Internet outside of school. Robust blended learning programs involve "anytime, anywhere" access to learning content for students—a major challenge in many communities. Perhaps the biggest hurdle confronting educators interested in blended learning, though, is the lack of a solid research base. As of now, there is still no definitive evidence that blended learning works (or doesn't.) While some studies have found encouraging results with specific programs or under certain circumstances, the question of whether blended learning positively impacts student learning still has a mostly unsatisfactory answer: "It depends."

CONCLUSION. Analysis of the dynamics of the effectiveness of completing tasks of high school tasks by junior schoolchildren in 2019-2023, gives us a unique opportunity to focus on the existing methodological deficiencies in the professional activities of primary school teachers and the educational shortcomings of junior schoolchildren that have taken root over several years [6;

7]. In addition, the interpretation of the results of the VPR allows us to give a comprehensive professional assessment of current trends, and most importantly, to begin to systematically resolve a pool of problems associated with improving the quality of education of students in accordance with the requirements of the updated primary school standard and the content of the FEP of the NEO.

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